

Machine Learning techniques and visualization tools for STM images at CNR-IOM labs

Tommaso Rodani

M.Sc. Data Science and Scientific Computing

University of Trieste

University of Udine

International School for Advanced Studies

Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics

Supervisor Prof. Stefano Cozzini
Second Supervisor Dr. Mirco Panighel

September 2020

Acknowledgements

Undertaking this thesis has been a truly life-changing experience for me and it would not have been possible to do without the support and guidance that I received from many people. Foremost, I am indebted to Professor Stefano Cozzini, my supervisor at the M.Sc. Data Science and Scientific Computing, whose continuous support, thoughtful criticism and intellectual demands guided this research from start to finish. I am particularly grateful for the valuable assistance given by researcher Dr. Mirco Panighel, my co-supervisor at the CNR-IOM, who informed my thinking and writing. Moreover, the STRAS research group coordinated by Dr. Cristina Africh and Prof. Giovanni Comelli at CNR-IOM provided me precious insights and I am therefore grateful to the dialogue exchanged. Researcher Dr. Alessio Ansuini provided me with useful and helpful discussion to address some of the methodological challenges of the thesis. I wish to acknowledge the continuous contribution provided by Dr. Alberto Cazzaniga with the experimental phase of this work. I want to express my special thanks to my colleague and friend Marco Franzon who shared his thinking, time, and care in developing this thesis. Furthermore, who kept a sense of humour when I had lost mine during these two years in the completion of the M.Sc. Data Science and Scientific Computing study. Finally, I wish to thank my family and friends for their support and encouragement throughout my study.

Abstract

This thesis reports the activities carried out on a scientific archive of scanning tunneling microscopy images with the objective of organizing it in a more structured and convenient dataset. The work, performed in strict cooperation with scientists, is framed within the urgent and relevant issue of a correct data management approach in the scientific research activity. The solutions developed in this thesis are designed around the European Commission guidelines on research data management, which follow a concise set of principles, known as the FAIR Data Principles. The problem was addressed using different tools and techniques, addressing several shortcomings of the original dataset, meeting the needs of the data producers from one side, and giving the dataset a broader audience perspective on the other.

In particular, the achievements of this work involve the creation of a database to store the scientific images metadata and the development of a web service to visually explore these metadata through interactive tools. Moreover, an analysis of the images and their representation led to the implementation of a novel technique to automatically detect and solve a particular type of image artifact. Finally, the focus of this thesis was dedicated to the development of a workflow for the labeling of the images based on the material composition of the measured samples. This goal was achieved using machine learning techniques, such as feature learning, to retrieve relevant images to help researchers in the manual labeling process. The complete source code used to reach the objectives of this thesis is open-source and publicly accessible (Rodani, 2020).

The thesis is organized as follows: chapter one shortly introduces the problem of scientific data management, frames the specific challenges faced in this work within the data management activities of CNR-IOM, and illustrates the necessary technical elements of STM images. The second chapter introduces the original dataset, de-

scribes the development steps of the metadata database creation, and discusses the enhancements made to improve researchers interaction with this new service. The third chapter illustrates the metadata web service and its integration in the Trieste Advance Data service (TriDAS) website, with particular attention to the metadata selection process and the further platform development. Chapter four describes the representation and common artifacts of images, presenting an original solution for one of them. It also describes the method of image labeling implemented together with the research group itself. Finally, chapter five draws some conclusions and then highlights some possible additional steps that can be performed on the dataset.

(Versione in italiano) Questa tesi espone la ricerca svolta su un archivio di immagini scientifiche ottenute da un microscopio a effetto tunnel, con l'obiettivo di organizzarlo in un dataset più strutturato e conveniente. Il lavoro, svolto in stretta collaborazione con i ricercatori, inquadra il problema rilevante e urgente di una corretta gestione dei dati nell'ambito dell'attività di ricerca scientifica. Le soluzioni sviluppate in questa tesi sono state progettate seguendo le linee guida della Commissione Europea sulla gestione dei dati di ricerca, che seguono una serie concisa di principi, noti come FAIR Data Principles. Il problema è stato indagato facendo uso di diversi strumenti e tecniche, affrontando diverse carenze del dataset originale, sia per soddisfare le esigenze dei ricercatori che in una prospettiva di pubblico più ampio. In particolare, i risultati di questo lavoro comprendono la creazione di un database per memorizzare i metadati delle immagini scientifiche e lo sviluppo di un servizio web per esplorare visivamente tali metadati attraverso strumenti interattivi. Inoltre, l'analisi delle immagini e della loro rappresentazione ha portato all'implementazione di una tecnica innovativa per rilevare e risolvere automaticamente un particolare tipo di artefatto dell'immagine. Infine, la tesi si è focalizzata sullo sviluppo di un processo di classificazione delle immagini in base alla composizione del materiale dei campioni misurati. Questo obiettivo è stato raggiunto utilizzando tecniche di machine learning, per recuperare immagini pertinenti da presentare ai ricercatori ed aiutarli nel processo di classificazione manuale. La tesi è organizzata nel modo seguente: il primo capitolo introduce brevemente il problema della gestione dei dati scientifici, inquadra le sfide specifiche affrontate in questo lavoro nell'ambito delle attività di gestione dei dati del CNR-IOM, e illustra gli elementi tecnici necessari delle immagini STM. Il secondo capitolo introduce il dataset originale, descrive le fasi di sviluppo della creazione del database di metadati e discute i miglioramenti apportati per migliorare l'interazione dei ricercatori con questo nuovo servizio. Il terzo capitolo illustra il servizio web dei metadati e la sua integrazione nel sito Trieste Advance Data (TriDAS), con particolare attenzione al processo di selezione dei metadati e all'ulteriore sviluppo della piattaforma. Il quarto capitolo descrive la rappresentazione e gli artefatti comuni delle immagini, presentando una soluzione originale per uno di essi ed alla fine espone il metodo di classificazione messo in pratica insieme al gruppo di

ricerca. Infine, il quinto capitolo trae alcune conclusioni e quindi evidenzia alcuni possibili miglioramenti che possono essere effettuati sul dataset.

Table of Contents

1	The scientific problem	1
1.1	Scientific Data Management problem and FAIR data	2
1.1.1	STM dataset FAIRification	4
1.2	Data repositories and data management infrastructure at CNR-IOM	6
1.2.1	NFFA EUROPE data management activities	7
1.2.2	SEM dataset	7
1.3	STM Images and the research at CNR-IOM	8
1.3.1	STM Operating Principle	8
1.3.2	CNR-IOM research on STM Images	10
2	STM Dataset and Database creation	12
2.1	STM Original Dataset	13
2.2	STM Database	15
2.3	Database interaction tools for researchers	19
3	Dataset exploration and visualization tools	20
3.1	Trieste Advance Data services	21
3.2	Metadata selection	23
3.3	STM explorer logic	24
3.4	Future development of the web service	27
4	Dataset analysis	30
4.1	Image preprocessing and presentation	31
4.2	Images Artifacts	33
4.3	STM categories and labeling process overview	38
4.4	Feature learning analysis	41
4.5	Improved labeling workflow based on image retrieval	48
5	Conclusions	54

List of Figures

1.1	Tunneling effect	8
1.2	STM microscope schematics	9
1.3	STM image example	10
1.4	Omicron VT-STM microscope at CNR-IOM laboratory	11
2.1	STRAS backup folder tree structure	13
2.2	metadata <i>.par</i> example	14
2.3	MySQL connection	15
2.4	<code>metadata_to_db()</code> function	16
2.5	<code>fix_columns_types()</code> function	17
2.6	<code>main()</code> function for new <code>clean_meta</code> table	18
3.1	TriDAS homepage	21
3.2	TriDAS folder tree structure	22
3.3	Quantile plot for <i>FieldXSizeinnm</i>	24
3.4	Scatter plot of <i>FieldXSizeinnm</i> and <i>FieldYSizeinnm</i>	25
3.5	Flask route for the STM database explorer	26
3.6	<code>bokeh_plot()</code> function	27
3.7	Metadata table view	28
3.8	Single image preview for the STM database explorer	28
3.9	Flask route for the metadata table view	29
4.1	<code>plot_by_ID()</code> function	31
4.2	Preprocessing steps overview: scan lines plots	32
4.3	Preprocessing steps overview: colormaps plots	33
4.4	Image artifacts: stripes and replicated patterns	34
4.5	Colormap error example	35
4.6	Colormap error example: slices of scan lines	35
4.7	<code>get_colormap_error()</code> function	36
4.8	Colormap error: percentage of colors lost due to outliers	37
4.9	Colormap error images: modified heatmaps	38

4.10	Category distribution of images	39
4.11	Monthly category distribution of images	40
4.12	<code>get_img_features_df()</code> function	43
4.13	First test: Euclidean distance, 500 trials, 20 images	45
4.14	Second test: Euclidean distance, 100 trials, 100 images	46
4.15	Extracted images example	49
4.16	Cosine similarity results	50
4.17	Distance matrices: representative images	51
4.18	Distance matrices: extracted images	52

List of Tables

- 4.1 Euclidean distance metric. Accuracy of first test, second test, and their difference. 47
- 5.1 Grouped images by category: coarse and manual labeling compared . 56

Chapter 1

The scientific problem

This chapter introduces the scientific problem addressed in this work and frames it within the general activities of the computational and data management group at CNR-IOM. In particular, the first section presents the general scientific problem of scientific data management and introduces the concept of FAIR data with particular attention to the FAIRification of the STM dataset. The second section illustrates the data infrastructure and the data analysis tools so far developed at CNR-IOM to cope with the complexity of data management. Then, it is discussed in more detail the challenges the current EU NFFA-EUROPE project poses in data management, the need for advanced machine learning tools, and well-defined procedures to produce and create FAIR scientific datasets. The final paragraph introduces the scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) technique to give the necessary technical elements to understand the forthcoming activities presented in the rest of the thesis and the original dataset, with the goal of make it FAIR through the tools and activities developed within this thesis.

1.1 Scientific Data Management problem and FAIR data

The last decades have shown a steadfast evolution in digital technologies leading to the Big Data paradigm, which expresses the continuous increase of produced data in volume, variety, and velocity (Laney, 2005). This revolution increased the need for reusability of data, especially in scientific research, where data infrastructures are usually specific for each research field and interoperable within the same domain at best. The potential of large-scale machine-analysis or new techniques like Artificial Intelligence can be used to discover new patterns and correlations between data from different research areas. However, it can be exploited only by adapting the existing data infrastructures to these evolving requirements. Data management rapidly became one of the main challenges in scientific research, especially in the long term. The simple publication of research data is not enough, and there is a need for community standards that span across all domains to make sure that data can be used beyond the borders of specific domains (European Commission, 2018). Some research communities reacted to these needs and created well-curated data repositories, like the Set of Identifications, Measurements, and Bibliography for Astronomical Data (SIMBAD) (Wenger et al., 1999) in the space sciences or the GenBank (Benson et al., 2013) and WorldWide Protein Data Bank (wwPDB) (Berman, Henrick and Nakamura, 2003) in the life sciences. However, these repositories are crafted around particular research fields, and each one of them has its dataset, datatypes, and software tools. Conversely, existing general-purpose repositories such as DataVerse (Magazine, 2011) or Zenodo (Zenodo, n.d.) have few requirements, and thus the discovery and interoperability of such heterogeneous data are more complex. According to the European Commission data guidelines (European Commission, 2016): "Open scientific research data should be easily discoverable, accessible, assessable, intelligible, usable and wherever possible interoperable to specific quality standards." From this guidelines, after a process of refinement through workshops and working groups, Wilkinson et al. published the FAIR Guiding Principles (Wilkinson, 2016), a set of high-level directives, which are not specific to any technology, standard or im-

plementation, that can be used to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, i.e., FAIR. The following briefly discusses the FAIR concepts, as reported in Wilkinson, 2016, and other reports and publications.

Findable data should have a unique and persistent identifier that can be used for reference and citations and should be described with rich metadata that includes the identifier of the underlying data. Given those directives, data registered in a search engine or indexed in a database can be discovered directly and indirectly from its metadata. The use of metadata to find relevant data allows both machines and users to retrieve different data types without providing specific information. Once some specific data is obtained, relevant information about its usage or references to related works can be found in its metadata, improving the search experience tremendously. Humans and machines can obtain accessible data through a standard protocol, which should be open and free in order to let everyone authorized to access the data from any device. In the case data is not open, its metadata should still be available. There is an essential distinction between FAIR and Open data: just publishing data is not enough to consider it FAIR, while FAIR data can be private or accessible only by a few authorized users. An example could be data that contains personal information like medical records, which should be anonymized and shared only under specific circumstances and protocols. Interoperable data and metadata should be described with precise vocabularies and standards, which should also be FAIR, to describe the meaning and content represented in the data. These unified ontologies are especially crucial for machine data retrieval, where a set of keywords can be used to discover data from different datasets and domains; these directives ensure that the knowledge represented by keywords remains the same across all research fields. Reusable data should be described with rich metadata and should also respect domain-specific community standards. Moreover, an explicit data usage license needs to be present, so both machines and users can act based on this information without risking copyright infringement. Finally, every data should provide information about provenance. As described by Gupta (Liu and Özsu, 2009), "Data provenance refers to a record trail that accounts for the origin of a piece of data (in a database, document or repository) together with an explanation of how and why it got to the present

place." These principles are at the core of scientific data management, and their integration in existing data infrastructures and research workflows is crucial for the benefit of the scientific community and private sector alike. As reported in several recent publications, making data FAIR (the so-called FAIRification) is a complex and challenging process. The generic workflow to make a dataset FAIR can be divided into different steps (Jacobsen et al., 2019):

- identify the FAIR objectives to be met,
- analyze data and metadata,
- define semantic data and metadata models,
- make data and metadata linkable,
- finally, host FAIR data.

The following subsection briefly points out the steps taken to make FAIR a dataset of scientific images obtained from a scanning tunneling microscope (STM).

1.1.1 STM dataset FAIRification

The current STM dataset does not meet any of the FAIR principles, and thus there are different objectives to achieve in the FAIRification process. The main goal regards the extraction of the instrument metadata present for every image of the dataset, which alone provides much useful information about the conditions in which images were obtained. These metadata are crucial to make images findable and accessible in successive steps, so the second step involves creating a database to store them. At this stage, images are, to some extent, already findable and accessible through their associated metadata, directly by querying the database or indirectly from other tools. Nonetheless, these instruments alone can be used only by the research group in charge of the dataset. Moreover, the technical expertise required to access STM images is still high, so the third step involves creating a website to let researchers explore the dataset visually through plots of the images metadata. This goal was reached by carefully selecting, together with researchers, the relevant metadata fields that would meet the semantic criteria of the domain-specific terms of microscopy

imagery. The website was then built around the selected metadata fields, which are searchable and presented through easy to understand graphs. Finally, the website was refined by linking the metadata to the underlying images so that researchers can visualize them directly on the browser without the need to use custom software. The last activity discussed in this work regards the most important contextual metadata of the STM dataset: the category in which the images belong, which indicates the type of materials that compose the sample. This crucial information is not recorded digitally; thus, machine learning techniques are used to infer it directly from the images. Obtaining this information can vastly improve the dataset value, which can then be reached by a broader audience, and also be used to develop deep learning analysis techniques for specific use cases.

1.2 Data repositories and data management infrastructure at CNR-IOM

This work has been performed at CNR-IOM(CNR-IOM, n.d.), where there is a small but active group that support IOM scientists, but not only, in managing scientific data. The group is actively involved in two EU-projects, EU NFFA-EUROPE (NFFA-EUROPE, n.d.) and EUSMI (EUSMI, n.d.), with the task to set up and maintain data infrastructure and develop associate data services. The critical component of data infrastructure available at CNR-IOM is the NextCloud tool (NextCloud, n.d.), which allows the sharing of scientific data among people, and on top of that, specific services can then be developed and made available. In the following are described the main services and tools available now on the CNR-IOM cloud infrastructure. NextCloud provides the data infrastructure for the EUSMI project, which provides scientific users all over Europe a distributed and integrate scientific infrastructure to experiment with soft matter. The EUSMI DRP, hosted at CNR-IOM, is directly accessible at <https://drp.eusmi-h2020.eu/> from EUSMI facilities to store and retrieve measurements obtained during an experiment. Every EUSMI user can access the platform with the same credentials as the official EUSMI portal. NextCloud instance installed on the CNR-IOM infrastructure automatically recognizes all EUSMI users and grants them access to their local repository. The EUSMI DRP offers data storage for each registered EUSMI user, with automatic metadata creation and update for all proposals accepted within the EUSMI project and Data policy management of the proposal accordingly to the data policy approved within the EUSMI consortium. CNR-IOM Datashare provides cloud services like file sharing and secure storage for its users. Researchers that host their data on this platform benefit from clear data retention, provenance, and licensing rules, therefore having efficient control on their produced data with the possibility to access, process, retrieve or share it at any time.

1.2.1 NFFA EUROPE data management activities

The NFFA-EUROPE (NFFA-EUROPE, n.d.) project is part of the Horizon 2020 EU funding program for research and innovation. This initiative aims to integrate and develop a unified and multidisciplinary research infrastructure for the world of nanoscience and involves more than twenty European research institutions coordinated by CNR-IOM (CNR-IOM, n.d.). Individual scientists and research groups can use NFFA-Europe Datashare and IDR (Information and Data management Repository Platform) to access and process their data as they provide more secure storage and retrieval medium. NFFA-Europe Datashare infrastructure, hosted on the local servers at the CNR-IOM, offers cloud services like secure file storage and sharing. The goal of IDR is to provide a repository for all relevant metadata of experiments and projects of the nanoscience community employing a structured online data catalog where users can access, share, and widely publish their data for a larger audience and other research groups. This service improves the reproducibility and reuse of scientific experimental results and permits large scale data processing to perform broader studies that are too costly for single research groups. These initiatives increase the scientific value of the data collected by making them available to a broader community for further analysis and fostering new collaborations between scientific groups.

1.2.2 SEM dataset

A perfect example that embodies this project is the publication of the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) dataset of the CNR-IOM (Aversa, Modarres et al., 2018), which consists of 22000 images manually classified into ten categories. This dataset is stored in the NFFA infrastructure, accessible through a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and searchable by metadata accordingly to the FAIR Guiding Principles. A classification service between these ten categories was developed using a neural network trained on the SEM dataset (Modarres et al., 2017). This service is publicly available and helps scientists automate the labeling of SEM images, which are produced by half of the research facilities of the NFFA consortium.

1.3 STM Images and the research at CNR-IOM

The scanning tunneling microscope (STM) was invented by Gerd K. Binnig and Heinrich Rohrer in 1981, and it is considered to be a breakthrough in the history of nanoscience as it leads to significant advances in the fields of nanotechnology, electrochemistry, semiconductor science, and molecular biology (Binnig et al., 1982) as it allowed scientists to see atoms on surfaces for the first time. This technique produces two-dimensional images of the surfaces of materials, down to the atomic scale. This chapter explains the fundamental concepts of the STM technique and then describe the one presently in use at the CNR-IOM research facility.

1.3.1 STM Operating Principle

Scanning tunneling microscopy is based on the tunneling effect of electrons. This is a quantum mechanics effect for which particles, in this case electrons, move through a barrier that they classically could not be able to overcome. In the scanning tunneling microscope, a sharp metal tip, ideally terminating with a single atom, scans the surface of a conducting sample at a distance of few Angstroms(\AA). When a bias voltage is applied, electrons can tunnel through the vacuum barrier between the tip and the sample and vice versa (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1: Electron wavefunction tunneling through a barrier, taken from (Nanoscience Instruments, n.d.)

STM can work in constant height mode, in which the distance between the tip and the sample remains constant while scanning. In this setting, as the tip scans the XY plane, the tunneling current intensity is recorded in a two-dimensional array $I(x; y)$. This method does not involve any feedback circuit controlling the tip position and, therefore, can be performed at higher speeds but carries the potential risk of the tip crashing on the sample surface. All the images in this work are obtained in constant current mode, in which, instead, the tip-sample distance is changed, so that the tunneling current is maintained fixed throughout the scan. In this mode, the images represent the vertical position required to keep the current constant, thus showing the surface topography. This measurement exploits the high sensitivity of the tunneling current, which decays exponentially with respect to the tip-sample distance. In the constant current mode, a feedback loop is required to maintain the tunneling current at a specific setpoint value. The feedback circuit is responsible for small adjustments of the vertical tip position during the scan. These little movements are possible because the tip is mounted on a piezoelectric tube, a special kind of material that can compress or elongate in response to voltage changes. Relatively high voltages correspond to tiny piezoelectric material changes, making possible movements in the order of picometres with extreme accuracy. Figure 1.2 shows a simple schematics of the main components of an STM microscope.

Figure 1.2: STM microscope schematics. Taken from (Werner et al., 2003)

More specifically, the current amplifier records the instantaneous value of the tunneling current, which is compared with a reference value by the feedback circuit. If the tunneling current is higher, the tip is too close to the sample surface; therefore, a voltage is applied to the piezo tube to withdraw the tip. The same process occurs when the tip-sample distance is too high; in this case, the voltage applied has the opposite sign. The Z value of the tip, as it moves over the XY plane, is recorded and can then be displayed as a line-scan image or as a 2D image (Figure 1.3), and it is interpreted as the surface topography of the sample.

Figure 1.3: Raw line-scan image, preprocessed line-scan, and 2d image

1.3.2 CNR-IOM research on STM Images

The STRAS research group activity is dedicated to the structural and electronic properties of solid surfaces at the nanoscale, with a specific interest in describing their evolution during surface processes. The laboratory, at the facility of Istituto Officina dei Materiali (CNR-IOM) of Trieste, hosts a commercial Omicron Variable Temperature STM (VT-STM) microscope (ScientaOmicron, n.d.), modified to improve mechanical stability and work under reaction conditions (Figure 1.4) which has been used to obtain the images presented in this thesis. The experimental apparatus is composed of one chamber for the sample preparation and one that hosts the microscope. Inside the chambers, the background pressure is maintained in the low 10^{-10} mbar range through a magnetic levitation turbo molecular pump, an ion getter

pump, and a Ti-sublimation pump. The microscope operating temperature ranges between 140K and 900K. The STM tip is mounted on a magnetic stage fixed on a single tube scanner with a maximum scan range of about $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}^2$ and a Z-travel of about $1 \mu\text{m}$. The sample is mounted with the surface pointing downwards with the tip reaching it from the bottom. During operation, the tip positioning is first adjusted manually with a CCD-camera aid; then, the final approach is performed automatically. Mechanical isolation is achieved using a spring system, which suspends the head of the STM. This instrument was used in the last two decades to obtain more than 100.000 images, which have been analyzed in this work.

Figure 1.4: Omicron VT-STM microscope at CNR-IOM laboratory. Courtesy of CNR-IOM, n.d.

Chapter 2

STM Dataset and Database creation

This chapter discusses the first steps taken toward the FAIRification of the STM dataset, which, as it is, does not meet any principle of the FAIR guidelines and it is quite challenging to use. Also, extracts of the Python code (Van Rossum and Drake, 2009) used to reach the objectives of this thesis are presented; the complete source code is open-source and publicly accessible (Rodani, 2020). In the first section is described the original dataset, consisting of a vast collection of STM measurements taken in the last two decades with the VT-STM at CNR-IOM. The organization and structure of this data needed to be addressed to make the STM dataset compatible with the FAIR principles, starting from the extraction of the instrument metadata associated with STM images. The second section reports the actions taken to make these critical pieces of information findable and accessible by creating a database reachable from any browser. This data service helps the discovery of images on the whole dataset by selecting different metadata values as filters. Nonetheless, there are some difficulties in the usability of this service, especially for scientists who lack the technical expertise needed to query databases. Finally, the third section describes the changes made to enhance this service, which was tailored around the needs of the research group in charge of the dataset. At the end of this process, researchers can easily access the metadata database with tools they are already familiar with, search and retrieve images from their metadata or insert new contextual metadata fields. These features already improve the value of the STM dataset significantly and show the importance of data management practice according to the FAIR principles.

2.1 STM Original Dataset

The STM backup folder stored on the NFFA Datashare contains all the measurements produced by the VT-STM at the STRAS laboratory since 1998 for a total of 244.7 GB and 431,000 files. It is organized in a tree structure based on date, with one folder for each year (YYYY), which contains a folder for every day of measurement of that year (YYYYMMDD), as shown in Figure 2.1. Inside each of these folders are contained the data daily taken at the laboratory.

Figure 2.1: STRAS backup folder tree structure

STM images are stored with different files and formats, but there is a straightforward naming convention, that was used to navigate the folders. For every image, it is stored a metadata file with the extension *.par*, which contains the instrument variables and other information in text format(Figure 2.2).

Data arrays are stored in binary format in files with extension *.tf0* or *.tb0*, one for two scan directions, so *.tf0* contains the forward scan while *.tb0* contains the backward scan. A typical image with both forward and backward scan arrays is stored in three files named *m1_ori.par*, *m1_ori.tb0*, *m1_ori.tf0*. The first step to extract the metadata involved parsing the whole backup folder and retrieve all the files with *.par* extension recursively, while ignoring directories outside the naming convention.

```

1;
2;           Omicron SPM Control.
3;           Parameter file for SPM data.
4;
5;
6 Format           : 1
7
8 Version          : V2.2
9 System          : SCALA
10
11;
12; User Information.
13;
14;
15 Date           : 07.05.10 10:48
16 User           : spm22
17 Comment        : -
18
19;
20; Scanner Description.
21;
22;
23 Name           : VT1_N.SCA
24 VGAP Contact   : TIP
25
26;
27; Scanner Area Description.
28;
29;
30 Field X Size in nm      : 30.0000      ;[nm]
31 Field Y Size in nm      : 30.0000      ;[nm]
32 Image Size in X        : 400
33 Image Size in Y        : 400
34 Increment X           : 0.0750000     ;[nm]
35 Increment Y           : 0.0750000     ;[nm]
36 Scan Angle            : 0.00000      ;[Degree]
37 X Offset              : 182.325       ;[nm]
38 Y Offset              : 270.975       ;[nm]

```

Figure 2.2: metadata *.par* example

Moreover, daily folders contains also other kind of STM measurements inside the directory or subdirectories. These measurements were ignored because their acquisition technique is different from the constant current mode used for the images of interest. Metadata extraction from *.par* text files was handled using a heavily customized version of the `load_meta()` function from the *omicronscala* module (Mirco Panighel, 2020a), a Python package to read the Omicron SCALA STM file format. For every image, it was created a Python dictionary that contains key/value pairs for each metadata. Also, path, filename, and image hash digest (md5) were added to be able to check for duplicates and retrieve images from storage.

2.2 STM Database

The STM database was built using MySQL (Widenius, Axmark and DuBois, 2002) on OpenStack (Sefraoui, Aissaoui and Eleuldj, 2012) of the CNR-IOM infrastructure and connected to phpMyAdmin (Delisle, 2012), a web-interface tool written in PHP for handling and administrating MySQL database. This design was chosen to share its contents with the TASC research group easily. The connection to the database was handled first using MySQL Connector/Python (J. W. Krogh, Krogh and Genick, 2018), a standardized database driver provided by MySQL. The code used to create the connection is shown in Figure 2.3, where `db_connection` initializes the connection while `db_cursor` is called to execute commands on the database inside that connection.

```
10 def database_connection():
11     """
12     Create an object used to open and manage a connection to a MySQL server,
13     send command and SQL statements and read the results.
14     """
15
16     db_connection = mysql.connector.connect(
17         host="IP_ADDRESS",
18         user="USER",
19         passwd="PASSWORD",
20         database="DB_NAME",
21         charset='utf8',
22         use_unicode=True)
23     db_cursor = db_connection.cursor()
24     db_cursor.execute("SET @@global.sql_mode= ' '")
25     return db_connection, db_cursor
```

Figure 2.3: MySQL connection

The function used to take the Python dictionary that contains the key-value pairs of image metadata and write them as a row into the database is reported below (Figure 2.4). The `metadata_to_db()` function creates columns dynamically on the database table if they are not already present. This workflow choice was driven by the nature of this dataset, which contains thousands of images with different metadata combinations. Few calls to the database, made with a bulk of images metadata was bound to errors due to the high probability of a conflicting set of metadata between

images, incorrect handling of corrupted files, and other exceptions. The flexibility of this solution justified the slower runtime caused by initiating a new connection to the database for every image, as it allows to develop changes in the metadata extraction functions as quickly as needed.

```
28 def metadata_to_db(meta: dict, table: str):
29     """
30     Connects to the database and write the metadata stored in meta
31     as a row in the table passed as string argument.
32     It automatically adds new columns if needed.
33     """
34     db_connection, db_cursor = database_connection()
35     db_cursor.execute("DESC TABLE_NAME")
36     columns = [x[0] for x in db_cursor.fetchall()]
37     for k, v in meta.items():
38         key = escape_strings(k)
39         value = escape_strings(v)
40         meta[key] = value
41     for key in meta.keys():
42         if key not in columns:
43             db_cursor.execute("ALTER TABLE {} ADD {} VARCHAR(255)".format(table,
44                                                                           key))
45
46     sql = "INSERT INTO (%s) (%s) VALUES ('%s')" % (table,
47                                                    ", ".join(meta.keys()),
48                                                    "'", "'".join(meta.values()))
49     db_cursor.execute(sql)
50     db_connection.commit()
51     return
```

Figure 2.4: `metadata_to_db()` function

The function `escape_string()` is used to escape special characters in a string for its use in an SQL statement; it basically prepends backslashes to special characters. At the end of the trial and error process, the `meta` table was populated with 111,423 rows and 204 columns, containing all the metadata of STM images. A quick check on the number of `NULLs` for each column showed that this large number of metadata columns originated from files related to measurements obtained with modes different than the constant current mode of interest. Another problem was the data type of each column, as values are written as string for all metadata fields. Two other Python libraries were used to address these problems: *pandas* (McKinney, 2010) and *SQLAlchemy* (Bayer, 2012). *Pandas* is an open-source Python package that provides

numerous tools for data analysis. The package comes with several data structures that can be used for many different data manipulation tasks. The *SQLAlchemy* package is used to map Python data types to database tables. Each column type of the database table is correctly modified by deriving it from the corresponding Python data type of the *pandas.DataFrame* column, making it the perfect solution for the data types problem. The STM database was downloaded and stored in a *pandas.DataFrame* object where it was manipulated to delete duplicates, remove rows of images that were recorded with different methods, and finally remove *NULLs* columns. The cleaned version of the database contains 64 columns instead of 204, while the number of images changed from 111,423 to 111,415.

```
1 import pickle
2 import pymysql
3 import sqlalchemy.types
4 from sqlalchemy import create_engine
5 import pandas as pd
6
7 def fix_columns_types(
8     df: pandas.DataFrame) -> dict:
9     """ Select the correct types for the MYSQL table columns, which are derived
10         from the DataFrame columns. Return a dictionary with column name as keys
11         and column type as values. """
12     dtypes_dict = {}
13     for column, dtype in zip(df.columns, df.dtypes):
14         if "object" in str(dtype):
15             dtypes_dict.update({column: sqlalchemy.types.NVARCHAR(length=255)})
16         if "datetime" in str(dtype):
17             dtypes_dict.update({column: sqlalchemy.types.DateTime()})
18         if "float" in str(dtype):
19             dtypes_dict.update({column: sqlalchemy.types.Float(precision=3,
20                                                                     asdecimal=True)})
21         if "int" in str(dtype):
22             dtypes_dict.update({column: sqlalchemy.types.INT()})
23     return dtypes_dict
```

Figure 2.5: `fix_columns_types()` function

The main function first creates a connection to MySQL, then loads the cleaned version of the STM database stored as a *pandas.DataFrame* in binary format using the built-in Python module *pickle*. Then `fix_column_types()` is called, which provides a mapping for the correct data type for each column of the database (Figure 2.5). Finally, the method `to_sql()` from *pandas.DataFrame* object, which makes use of

SQLAlchemy, writes the STM metadata to the new table `clean_meta`; the whole process in the main function is shown in Figure 2.6.

```
26 def main():
27
28     # Create connection object to MYSQL db
29     db_connection_str = 'mysql+pymysql://user:passwd@host/stm_images'
30     db_connection = create_engine(db_connection_str)
31
32     # Load clean metadata dataframe
33     with open('clean_meta.pkl', 'rb') as f:
34         clean_meta = pickle.load(f)
35
36     # write dataframe in new table "clean_meta"
37     columns_dtype = fix_column_types(clean_meta)
38     clean_meta.to_sql('clean_meta', db_connection, index = False,
39                       dtype = columns_dtype)
```

Figure 2.6: `main()` function for new `clean_meta` table

2.3 Database interaction tools for researchers

The interaction protocol with the STM database by researchers was designed at first around phpMyAdmin (Delisle, 2012), through which authenticated users can interact directly with the database with a comprehensive GUI interface within a browser. Although flexible and user-friendly, this solution was not optimal as phpMyAdmin is meant to be an admin panel and offers much more advanced functionalities than those needed. Researchers needed only to perform simple queries and occasionally insert tags in a few database columns. Moreover, the typical workflow of analysis involved *jupyter-notebook* (Kluyver et al., 2016), an open-source web application used to create and share documents that contain code, equations, visualizations, and explanatory text, using Python as the kernel interpreter. Due to the use case of the database and the working environment, another approach was chosen to let researchers interact with the database using Python directly within *jupyter-notebook*. The first challenge of this setup was security, as the database is hosted within an instance of MySQL shared with other users on a machine in a private network. Instead of using a Virtual Network Provider (VPN) to access MySQL from Python directly, the connection from outside the local network was handled using a jumpbox, a system on a network used to access and manage devices in a separate security zone. In this two-step solution, the user authentication is handled using *ssh-keys* to connect to the jumpbox, where the connection to MySQL is hardcoded.

Chapter 3

Dataset exploration and visualization tools

The STM database contains now, in an organized way, useful metadata for researchers to quickly find relevant images. However, it is fundamental to provide scientists a web service to facilitate and simplify the search process. This web service, named *STM Explorer* and presented in this chapter, is a tool that researchers can use to interact visually with the metadata database. Such service is integrated on the Trieste Advance Data Services website (TriDAS, n.d.), designed to enable advanced data services connected to scientific data resources to help researchers in their work. In this chapter, the first section shows the TriDAS website development steps. The most important metadata fields to be used in the web service, selected together with researchers, are described in detail in the second section. Then, in the third paragraph, the graphs that compose the metadata explorer and the associated Python code are shown with some examples. The fourth section presents the evolution from just the visualization of metadata to the direct interaction with images. This concept is shown through a working demo, where metadata fields for some groups of images are retrieved and presented in a table. In this table, new functions permit additional filtering based on metadata and images can be visualized directly on the browser without custom software. The web app lets researchers browse images from their linked metadata and visualize them effortlessly, with the potential to reach a much broader audience. This functionality can be extended to allow scientists to add new metadata information in the database directly from the web app: this and

other enhancements that can further improve the *FAIRness* of the STM dataset are discussed in the final considerations of the paragraph.

3.1 Trieste Advance Data services

Figure 3.1: TriDAS homepage

Trieste Advance Data Services (TriDAS) aims to act as a hub from which researchers can access several data services (Figure 3.1). These can be classified into two broad categories: (i) data services developed within specific experimental or computational techniques and (ii) data services developed to address a specific class of scientific data, like images or 3D archives. An example of the first kind of service is the Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) classifier (Classifier, n.d.), developed at CNR-IOM, which uses machine learning to tag automatically SEM images and it is optimized for such technique. The second class of services addresses the broad field of scientific images coming from many distinct sources: for instance, users can access two database exploration tools, one for STM images and another for SEM images. TriDAS is under development, and by the time being, it uses *Flask* (Grinberg, 2018), a Python web application framework. It is designed to get started quickly and easily, with the ability to scale up to complex applications. It does not have built-in database interaction, but the *flask-sqlalchemy* extension library can be used to connect SQL databases to a *Flask* application, making it the perfect candidate for this website. It is important to note that TriDAS is an ongoing project and, in this section, presents and discusses its first public release, available at <https://tridas.nffa.eu/>. Being

public, this release is not directly connected to the CNR-IOM full scientific databases due to privacy and security reasons. Instead, a static version of the database contents is provided, served to the web app as *pandas.DataFrame*, and saved in binary *pickle* format. The layout of the web app is shown in Figure 3.2, where the *app* folder contains the application logic. The *static* folder contains the database file, *clean_meta.pkl*, and other static resources as images and *JavaScript* code; finally, the *templates* folder contains all the HTML files.

Figure 3.2: TriDAS folder tree structure

3.2 Metadata selection

The core logic of the web service is designed around the metadata of the images, and a careful selection of the most important fields is crucial for its success. Users interacting with the platform can find relevant images utilizing just the selected metadata fields without providing specific information. Therefore, the subset of metadata should provide descriptive information about the context, quality, and characteristics of the linked images. Only a strict cooperation with domain experts can ensure a correct metadata selection that represents the knowledge of the specific research area. In our case, all 65 metadata fields present in the database provide information automatically generated by the STM microscope or produced in the database creation. Most of these fields provide little information about the context or quality of the images as they describe settings related only to the microscope used. Nonetheless, a thorough analysis performed together with researchers selected nine metadata fields, which provide significant information about image characteristics and microscope settings relevant to image quality and context. In the following is a brief description of the selected metadata fields:

- *FieldXSizeinnm* and *FieldYSizeinnm*, which are the X and Y dimensions in nanometers of the scan size of each image.
- *XOffset* and *YOffset*, which are the X and Y coordinates of the tip offset in nanometers from the center of the scan axes.
- *ScanSpeed*, which is the speed measured in nanometers per second of the scan.
- *ScanAngle*, which is the rotation angle of the fast scan direction in the XY plane measured in degrees; it is zero when the fast scan direction is along the absolute X -axis.
- *GapVoltage*, it is the bias voltage applied between tip and sample in the constant current scan mode, measured in Volts.
- *LoopGain*, it is the integral term of the PID feedback loop controller of the tunneling current.

- *FeedbackSet*, it is the setpoint of the tunneling current, measured in nanoamperes. Currently not implemented in the public version of the service.

3.3 STM explorer logic

The metadata database exploration tool, developed as an integrated service within TriDAS for STM images, allows users to visually explore the images metadata through interactive and downloadable plots. These plots are built using *Bokeh* (Bokeh Development Team, 2020), a Python interactive visualization library that targets modern web browsers for presentation. There are two kinds of plots available: a quantile plot for single metadata fields and a scatter plot that show the distribution of images between two chosen metadata fields. The quantile plot shows the number of images and the metadata values interval for each quantile (Figure 3.3). The subtitle shows the metadata coverage for the dataset, which is the percentage of images with that particular metadata value.

Figure 3.3: Quantile plot for *FieldXSizeinnm*

The scatter plot gives a visual intuition on the number of images in the different combinations of the two chosen metadata fields by the radius of the underlying circles, which is a function of the number of images and the metadata value field (Figure 3.4). In both plots, hovering on top of plot objects creates a pop up that shows information about that object: the number of images and value intervals for quantiles plots and the number of images and metadata value for each field in the scatter plot. The right toolbar lets users interact with the plots by moving, zooming in and out, and saving plots as images.

Figure 3.4: Scatter plot of *FieldXSizeinmm* and *FieldYSizeinmm*

These dataset exploration tools help the researchers to quickly analyze data visually without dealing with the technical expertise required to interact directly with databases. The *SQLAlchemy* integration of Flask takes care of the connection with databases, while the *Bokeh* visualization library presents the information in a general format independent of the underlying data structure. This framework can be quickly adapted to offer access to different scientific databases in order

to explore any data visually. The relevant code of *Flask* application that manages the logic of the STM Image Explorer page is shown in Figure 3.5, where the function `get_chosen_metadata()` retrieves the metadata information and the `bokeh_plot()` function returns the plot to be rendered in the HTML page.

```
20 @app.route('/dashboard_stm/', methods=['GET', 'POST'])
21 def show_dashboard():
22     total = len(stm)
23     x_ax = request.form.get('X')
24     y_ax = request.form.get('Y')
25     plots = []
26     if x_ax == y_ax:
27         y_ax = None
28     axis = get_axis(x_ax, y_ax)
29     if not axis:
30         return render_template('dashboard_stm.html', plots=plots)
31     metadata = get_chosen_metadata(stm, axis)
32     plot = bokeh_plot(metadata, total)
33     plots.append(plot)
34     return render_template('dashboard_stm.html', plots=plots)
35
```

Figure 3.5: Flask route for the STM database explorer

The `bokeh_plot()` function chooses between the two plot types based on user input, add styling attributes, and wraps the plots in an *HTML div* to be rendered correctly. The version in Figure 3.6 contains a *url* variable and a method not present in the current implementation, but it is shown here as this piece of code is fundamental for the application described in the next paragraph, which shows a working demo of the next proposal through which researchers can directly interact with the database.

```

91 v def bokeh_plot(metadata, total):
92     df = metadata
93     axis = metadata.columns
94     url = ''
95
96 v     if len(axis) == 2:
97         plot, hover, title = get_quantile_plot(df, axis, total)
98 v     else:
99         plot, hover, title, url = get_scatter_plot(df, axis)
100
101 v     plot.add_layout(Title(text='{}'.format(title), text_font_style="bold",
102                             text_font_size="16pt"), 'above')
103     plot.add_tools(hover)
104
105 v     if url != '':
106         taptool = plot.select(type=TapTool)
107         taptool.callback = OpenURL(url=url)
108
109     script, div = components(plot)
110     return script, div

```

Figure 3.6: bokeh_plot() function

3.4 Future development of the web service

The publicly available STM database explorer shows the distribution of the most interesting metadata fields, but, as it is, it can provide only a general overview of the images. In order to improve the usability and the research value of the dataset, the user experience cannot be limited to visualization. The *Bokeh* library can be used to develop interaction with the graphs in a visually intuitive way, both by browsing or adding information to the underlying database. An example of this kind of interaction is the possibility to click on a specific metadata combination in the scatter plot and be redirected to a new page that retrieves the most important metadata fields for each image that have that combination, as shown in Figure 3.7.

In this page, researchers can select, order, filter, and search images based on their metadata values, without having to query a database. The *ID* column consists of each image unique identifier in the database and, by clicking on it, the corresponding STM image is rendered and showed in a new tab, with date and image name as the title (Figure 3.8).

STM Images List

Show 10 entries Search:

ID	Date	Categories	FieldXSizeinnm	FieldYSizeinnm	ScanAngle	GapVoltage	FeedbackSet	LoopGain	ScanSpeed	XOffset	YOffset
92973	1999-01-15	O_Rh110	300.0	300.0	0.0	0.103674	0.947542	2.00000	3000.00	-175.33800	1000.25000
92124	1999-02-08	O_Rh110	300.0	300.0	0.0	0.537159	1.000000	1.98180	3000.00	376.25000	-2512.75000
92134	1999-02-08	O_Rh110	300.0	300.0	0.0	-0.600000	1.019000	1.00000	3000.00	-1000.00000	-1864.20000
89128	1999-08-31	O_Rh110	300.0	300.0	0.0	0.423552	0.965021	3.29342	4411.76	-3413.65000	3341.77000
90970	1999-11-24	O_Rh110	300.0	300.0	0.0	0.500000	1.000000	1.52178	3000.00	3414.75000	-2731.75000
90971	1999-11-24	O_Rh110	300.0	300.0	0.0	0.500000	1.000000	1.52178	3000.00	3300.00000	-2800.00000
90994	1999-11-24	O_Rh110	300.0	300.0	0.0	0.020000	1.000000	2.33156	3000.00	2000.00000	-3800.00000
90998	1999-11-24	O_Rh110	300.0	300.0	0.0	0.500000	1.000000	3.03636	3000.00	4000.00000	-2000.00000
91000	1999-11-24	O_Rh110	300.0	300.0	0.0	0.500000	1.000000	1.52178	3000.00	3300.00000	-2800.00000
91012	1999-11-24	O_Rh110	300.0	300.0	0.0	0.500000	1.000000	1.52178	3000.00	3300.00000	-2800.00000

Showing 1 to 10 of 814 entries First Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 82 Next Last

Figure 3.7: Metadata table for images with both *FieldXSizeinnm* and *FieldYSizeinnm* equal to 300.

Figure 3.8: Single image preview for the STM database explorer

The main components of Flask application that oversee these new functionalities are briefly presented below, where the `bokeh_plot()` function uses the *TapTool* callback to redirect users from an object in the scatter plot to the *Flask* route responsible for the metadata table page (Figure 3.9).

This route retrieves all images metadata for the current selection, which for this demo is bounded at 1000 images, and returns them in a new HTML page. The table layout, filter options, and search bar of this table view page (Figure 3.7) are rendered through *JavaScript* code, while the single image visualization function (Figure 3.8) is implemented as another *Flask* route that returns the image directly in a POST request.

```
37 @app.route('/dashboard_stm/images/', methods=['GET', 'POST'])
38 def show_metadata_table():
39     x = request.args.get('x')
40     y = request.args.get('y')
41     xval = request.args.get('xval')
42     yval = request.args.get('yval')
43     cols = [x, y]
44     values = [xval, yval]
45     imgs = filter_df_columns(stm, cols, values).sort_values('Date')
46     # demo show only 1000 random images
47     if len(imgs) > 1000:
48         imgs = imgs.sample(1000)
49     return render_template(
50         'stm_images.html',
51         tables=[imgs.to_html(table_id="STM",
52                             index=False, bold_rows=False,
53                             classes='table table-bordered table-striped',
54                             header="true")])
```

Figure 3.9: Flask route for the metadata table view

This workflow, from the scatter plot to the single image view, lets users search and visualize images based on their metadata value effortlessly, reducing the technical debt while improving sharing and usability. The implementation provided above is quite simple and involves a read-only interaction with the database, as it works as a demonstration for the potential and further development of the platform. In a real production environment, this web application, backed up by a user management system, can foster research activities by letting users share data and write new contextual metadata in addition to the instrument metadata already collected, thus enriching the dataset while maintaining strict control of access and data provenance.

Chapter 4

Dataset analysis

In this chapter the dataset is analyzed in more detail, with special attention to two particular issues: one regarding image artifacts and the other involving missing metadata. The first section outlines the typical processing steps needed to visualize an STM image correctly and introduces the most common artifacts for this imaging technique. Lastly, an analysis of one of these artifacts is performed on the dataset, and a novel automated solution to solve it is presented. The following sections describe the process to retrieve the most crucial metadata that is remarkably missing: the information about the category in which the images belong, which indicates the type of materials that compose the sample. The second section outlines the first approach to solve this problem, consisting of different iteration of manual labeling of the images, from a coarse division to a fine-grained one, which unfortunately cannot be completed because it is too time-consuming. The third paragraph describes the use of the manually obtained labels and the evaluation of the performance of a common machine learning technique using statistical analysis. This analysis is necessary due to the sensible differences between a typical use case on real-world images and the specific application on the STM dataset. As the analysis shows a positive outcome, the fourth section reports the use of this machine learning technique to create a new, more automated workflow to obtain exact labels for several images.

4.1 Image preprocessing and presentation

All the STM images analyzed were acquired using an Omicron VT-STM microscope in constant current mode. They can be interpreted as the surface topography of the sample, where the Z value of the tip represents, in first approximation, the height of the sample at that XY coordinates. This data is saved as an array of XY dimensions, where in every element the Z value, or height, of the tip is stored. In particular, a single forward line scan through the sample records the Z value of the tip in a row of the array. Afterward, the corresponding backward line scan is recorded in another file, again as a row of the array. The tip is then moved laterally to scan the next line on the sample surface; this process is repeated Y times to complete the scan. The results are two files, one for the forward scan and another for the backward scan. These can be drawn directly as line-scan images or preprocessed first and then plotted as a 2d image. The *spym* Python package (Mirco Panighel, 2020b) is used to process images and plot them correctly in 2d colormaps, as shown in the function `plot_by_ID()` in Figure 4.1.

```
130 def plot_by_ID(df, path, ID):
131     img = df.loc[ID]
132     date = img.Date
133     fname = img.TF0_Filename
134     file = img.ImageOriginalName
135
136     # Load image as xarray object
137     ds = omicronscala.to_dataset(Path(path+file))
138
139     # get forward scan array
140     tf = ds.Z_Forward
141
142     # preprocessing steps
143     tf.spym.align()
144     tf.spym.plane()
145     tf.spym.fixzero(to_mean=True)
146
147     # Generate plot
148     fig = plt.figure(figsize=(16,16))
149     axis = fig.add_subplot(1, 1, 1)
150     tf.plot(ax=axis, cmap='afmhot', add_colorbar=False)
151     axis.set_title(r"[{}] {} $\bf{{{}}}$".format(date, fname, ID), fontsize=16)
152     plt.show()
```

Figure 4.1: `plot_by_ID()` function

The scan lines are aligned together, then a plane is fitted through them, and finally, their Z values are fixed so that the zero corresponds to the mean Z value of the image.

An example of the preprocessing steps and their modification of the scan lines is depicted in Figure 4.2, where the first row shows respectively the raw lines, the aligned lines, the lines fitted through a plane, and finally, the lines with the zero fixed to their mean value. The second row shows the same plots but on a common axis range, to better show the different steps of the preprocessing.

Figure 4.2: Preprocessing steps overview: scan lines plots

The 2D colormap equivalent of the lines scan plots shown above is outlined in Figure 4.3, where at every step of the preprocessing, the resulting image appears more defined. The first two steps, line alignment and plane fitting, are essential for reducing the range of values of the image in an appropriate interval for a 2D color mapping. It is clearer from the difference between the last two images that set the zero at the median Z value is beneficial for heatmaps, to express with the whole gradient of colors each height steps.

Figure 4.3: Preprocessing steps overview: colormaps plots

4.2 Images Artifacts

In carrying out an STM measurement, it is not uncommon to find the presence of defects and artifacts in the final image, due to the impossibility to operate in ideal conditions and without any impurities in the sample, tip, or measurement environment. Artifacts can present themselves in different ways, depending on the phenomenon from which they originate. A type of artifact that can occur is determined by the rapid passage of an atom on the surface below the tip or, alternatively, a sudden change in the tip apex atomic configuration. This event causes a transient in the current value, which completely masks the real topography of the surface at the points involved. This artifact typically manifests itself as a long line of significantly higher (or lower) intensity, with respect to the lines immediately above and below, direct along the STM scan direction. A representative example of this artifact can be seen in the horizontal stripes across the left image of Figure 4.4. The characteristics of the tip are a crucial element in the success of a good STM image: in the ideal case, the tip ends with a single atom and it is therefore ensured that only that atom is responsible for registered tunneling current. Otherwise, with a tip less sharp, more atoms of the tip may contribute to the tunneling current, causing a lower lateral resolution. Often, however, the tip can also end with two or more appendices of atomic size, each of which acts as a probe during the scan: the resulting image will have a replication of the structures present on the surface for each appendix of the tip, as it can be seen in the right image of Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Image artifacts: stripes and replicated patterns

In general, the second artifact can be quite challenging to detect, as it can affect the image quality marginally. On the other hand, the first artifact is usually visible at first glance, but its influence in the image quality can have different severity. Thus, identifying this distortion is not enough to deem an image as flawed, and a careful assessment of its gravity is required for every image. For example, an image with a few short stripes can be considered valid as their overall quantity is negligible, while the same type of error in another image can be enough to consider it defective. As these artifacts depend on the context in which the image is recorded, an automatic detection algorithm is difficult to implement and can only be used as a companion tool in assessing the error and not as a discriminant of it. However, extreme cases of the first artifact and current spikes can result in information loss when displaying the whole image topography. The core of this problem are the Z values recorded in the points of the distorted lines, which can be of orders of magnitude higher in absolute value from the other data points. These outliers expand the interval of Z values so that the topography information in other scan lines disappears when the images are visualized as heatmaps. The cause of this data loss derives from the fact that heatmaps transform the image data using a colormap, which maps data values to colors. In the presence of outliers, all the other data points are mapped in a single

or few colors. This fact is evident by looking at Figure 4.5, where the Z values on one line are so much apart from each other that the resulting colormap image has almost the same color for all other scan lines.

Figure 4.5: Colormap error: scan lines raw, scan lines after preprocessing, heatmap

However, this kind of image can be of some value and should not be disregarded, as it is shown in Figure 4.6, where the same image as above is rendered in slices. This method shows that slices in which the outliers are not present show the topography information while the problematic slice displays the same constant appearance of the previous figure.

Figure 4.6: Colormap error: slices of scan lines raw and heatmap

These images cannot be used right away, but they still contain the sample topography information, so it is important to identify them, see how many images are affected by this error, and assess a possible solution to this problem. The answer to the detection of images affected by the colormap error lies in finding the outliers in the Z values data array. This problem can be solved with different techniques. A novel method developed in this work is shown in Figure 4.7, where the function `get_colormap_error()` returns the percentage of colors lost.

```
200 v def get_colormap_error(df, ID):
201     meta, img = imgID(df, ID)
202     data = img.data
203
204     # max and min vectors of rows
205     max_row = np.amax(data, axis=0)
206     min_row = np.amin(data, axis=0)
207
208     # median max and min for image
209     min_median = np.median(min_row)
210     max_median = np.median(max_row)
211
212     #diff max/min rows of image
213     diff = (max_row - min_row)
214
215     for i in range(1,100):
216         # treshold to define wrong image
217         treshold = (max_median - min_median) * (255 * (1 - (i * 0.01)))
218         cmap_error = np.where(diff > treshold)[0]
219 v         if len(cmap_error) > 0:
220             return 100-i
221     return 0
```

Figure 4.7: `get_colormap_error()` function

More specifically, the colormap error is encoded in an integer with value 0-100, so when this value is zero, the image is not affected by this problem, while, as an example, an image with this value equal to 20 has 20% of its color space lost, so 50 values out of 255. The threshold to identify an image as correct depends on the difference between the median values of the rows that contain the maximum and minimum value of the image, respectively.

This threshold is decreased at every iteration to detect the exact amount of color lost in percentage, so when the difference between the maximum row and minimum row is greater than the threshold, this percentage, encoded as an integer, is returned. The analysis of this error on the STM dataset is shown in Figure 4.8, where the number of images affected is reported on a logarithmic scale as their amount quickly decreases with respect to the percentage of colors lost.

Figure 4.8: Colormap error: percentage of colors lost due to outliers

These results are reassuring, as there is only a small number of images with high colormap error. For example, images with colormap error equal to or greater than 20% are just 255, while all images with an error greater than 5% are 1677. The colormap error gives essential information on the image quality and has been recorded in a new metadata field. Moreover, the `plot_by_ID()` function presented in Figure 4.1 was modified to act based on this information: if the colormap error is present, the 2nd and 98th percentiles of the data are used to compute the color limits. This method excludes the outliers and results in a good representation of the images, as shown in Figure 4.9. The first row is composed of images with colormap error

greater than 20% plotted without any modification, while in the second row, the same images are plotted with the new method to compute color limits.

Figure 4.9: Images with Colormap error greater than 20. The first row plotted normally; the second row plotted with a modified color limits method.

4.3 STM categories and labeling process overview

One of the most interesting information of the dataset is the category to which each image belongs, which indicates the type of materials that compose the sample, for example, *Gr_Ni110*, that is graphene (Gr) on a particular crystallographic surface (110) of nickel (Ni). Surprisingly enough, such important information is not registered as scientific metadata within the STM images, but it is only manually annotated by researchers in the laboratory paper logbook. This fact is a clear indication of an inadequate data management approach that requires an enormous amount of work to handle if integrated by hand. The dataset discussed in this work collects the work done in twenty years of research at the STM laboratory. Therefore, it is mandatory to develop some automatic or semiautomatic tools and procedures

to retrieve information on samples avoiding a long and difficult manual process. In the following, it is described the approach developed in strict cooperation with the researchers. The starting point was to manually label groups of images into sample categories. Researchers, within the same day, work typically on samples of the same category, and, considering the typical workflow of the group, it is then reasonably fair to assume that samples should be of the same category also within a limited time period. Given these assumptions, the activity of the research group was tracked throughout the period, and a tentative division of the dataset in broad categories was derived. This starting point was good enough to approximate the number of categories, between 10 and 20, and their respective acquisition periods, ranging from several months to a few years. From this first approximation, plots of 100 randomly chosen images for each month of all 20 years were generated and then given to researchers to be manually labeled, with the aim to verify and correct the first rough subdivision.

Figure 4.10: Category distribution of images

The result of this process is presented in Figure 4.10, where the number of categories is 18. The total number of labeled images is around 90%, while the remaining 10% left without a known category, indicated here as *mixed* and depicted in red. The monthly categories distribution after the manual labeling of each month is shown

in Figure 4.11, in which each category has the same color as the previous figure, so again the unknown images are depicted as red.

Figure 4.11: Monthly category distribution of images

From this distribution, the assumption that, within a limited time period, the research group works with the same sample category seems verified. On the other hand, other issues arise. There is a high variance in the number of images obtained each month, as, in some cases, the amount of the images reaches almost 3000. For these months, a single plot with only 100 images counts roughly to the 3% of the total, so it is possible that it is not representative of all images taken in that period. Moreover, it is not clear for those months falling between two categories when the switch from one material to another has taken place. These problems were addressed in a second labeling process, by generating new plots for all images in the dataset, in which, for each day, all images in groups of 100 and the remaining modulo are plotted. The aggregation of images in groups was chosen in the first place to help researchers in the labeling process, so they can see at first glance the category of each group of 100 images and, at the same time, the correct category association for those months with a very high number of images. This choice is more appropriate with respect to a single image view because there is a high number of similar images in the dataset, as, for example, a sequence of images taken to record a reaction or with different microscope parameters to improve image quality. Still, the number of days of the dataset is 1470, while the number of months is 190 and, as a consequence, this labeling process is an order of magnitude greater from the previous one, which took one month to complete. Indeed, this refined labeling process is still very time consuming and thus challenging to finalize, but its completion should result in a

higher precision on category association, down to the single day, which, as for the first initial claim, would also correspond to an accurate labeling.

4.4 Feature learning analysis

The previously proposed solution of manual labeling is not reasonably applicable due to the enormous amount of work it requires, so, in the next paragraphs, it is described another approach that involves more automation based on machine learning techniques. This approach is based on *representation learning* (Bengio, Courville and Vincent, 2013), which is a set of methods that allows a machine to be fed with raw data and automatically discover the representation needed for detection or classification. This representation is obtained through a convolutional neural network (LeCun et al., 1989), which is a class of deep learning neural networks (Goodfellow et al., 2016) generally applied to image recognition and other visual tasks. Deep learning neural networks are models made up of different layers of computational units called neurons. These layers transform the representation at one level, starting from the raw data input into a representation at a higher and slightly more abstract level (LeCun, Bengio and Hinton, 2015). More specifically, in convolutional neural network models, the first layers capture low-level image features like edges, while higher layers capture finer details. The image representation at each layer is the output vector of the transformation applied by its neurons to the representation of the previous layer and is generally called features vector (Bishop, 2006). The features present in the last layers of the network are commonly assumed to capture information that is relevant for solving the addressed problem, in this case, image classification. The transformation applied is dependent on the parameters stored in the neurons, called weights, which must be tuned in a training phase to minimize the error, called loss function, of the specific task. The training is usually time-consuming, compute-intensive, and needs a large amount of data. Transfer learning (Pan and Yang, 2010) aims to overcome this limitation by creating methods to transfer knowledge from one task to another. In neural networks, this technique is used to transfer the learned weights of a base network, trained on a large dataset, to a target

network on a new problem. In this case, transfer learning is used on the target STM dataset starting from a CNN pre-trained on the dataset ImageNet (Deng et al., 2009), an extensive visual database used in visual recognition research. Models trained on ImageNet appear to capture details that are generally relevant in any image classification tasks (Modarres et al., 2017). Based on this evidence, a ResNet-50 model pre-trained on ImageNet was used to extract the features of the STM dataset images. ResNet stands for Deep Residual Network (He et al., 2016), a type of convolutional neural network with an identity connection between layers, which, roughly speaking, allows the stacking of more layers by optimizing the backpropagation of the learned weights using this connection. The features were extracted from the ResNet50 from the input of the last but one linear layer of the network, which consists of a vector of length 4096. This process was implemented in Python using *fastai* (Howard and Gugger, 2020), a deep learning library that provides high-level components focused on ease of use without compromising flexibility and performance. It is built on top of *PyTorch* (Paszke et al., 2019), one of the most popular Python machine learning frameworks. The code relevant for features retrieval is shown in Figure 4.12, where at every iteration of the `get_img_features_df()` loop, the model is trained up to the chosen layer on the GPU, and then the features of several images determined by the `batch_size` variable are transferred to the main memory. The use of GPU drastically speeds up the compute time from a few hours to 5 minutes in this case. At the end of the loop, the features of all the images are saved in the features dictionary and stored in a *pandas.DataFrame* together with relevant metadata such as image path, image ID, label, and `label_id`, which is an integer that identifies the label.

In general, the approach sketched above does work well for generic images representing the real world. As the model used was pre-trained on ImageNet, the extracted features should reasonably represent well real-world images, and it should be possible to use these features to classify the images into different categories. Unfortunately, this is not the case for scientific images like STM images and SEM images, which are, in general, quite far from natural scene images. Microscopy images in materials science have featured characters, which make the task of microscopic imaging analysis very different and challenging (Ge et al., 2020). In contrast to real-world images,

```

42 def get_img_features_df(linear_output_layer, inference_data_loader, batch_size):
43     features = {}
44
45     with Hook(linear_output_layer, get_input, True, True) as hook:
46         for i, (images, labels) in enumerate(inference_data_loader):
47             n_imgs = images.shape[0]
48             if n_imgs != batch_size:
49                 img_ids = inference_data_loader.items[-n_imgs:]
50             else:
51                 img_ids = inference_data_loader.items[i * n_imgs:(i + 1) * n_imgs]
52             model.eval()(images)
53             images_features = hook.stored.cpu().numpy()
54             images_features = images_features.reshape(n_imgs, -1)
55             for img_id, img_features in zip(img_ids, images_features):
56                 features[img_id] = img_features
57
58     features_df = pd.DataFrame(features.items(), columns=['img_path', 'img_repr'])
59     features_df['ID'] = [x.split('/')[-1].split('.')[0] for x in features_df['img_path']]
60     features_df.set_index('ID', inplace=True)
61     features_df['label'] = [inference_data.classes[x] for x in inference_data.train_ds.y.items[0:features_df.shape[0]]]
62     features_df['label_id'] = inference_data.train_ds.y.items[0:features_df.shape[0]]
63     return features_df

```

Figure 4.12: `get_img_features_df()` function

microscopy images generally have distortions and significant noise and are usually in a single channel format that is grayscale or use a color gradient, instead of the standard three-channel RGB of natural images. Given these characteristics of microscopic imaging in material science with respect to the general application of deep learning techniques on natural world imagery, further analysis of the representation quality of STM images was required. The general assumption that features extracted from ImageNet are relevant in any image classification task must be verified in this circumstance, as the knowledge transferred from the pre-trained model was learned by training on natural images. The method used to validate the extracted features is based on Content-based image retrieval (CBIR), which aims to search images by analyzing their visual contents (Wan et al., 2014). In this context, a distance metric is calculated between a representation of the base image and the representation of every other image in the dataset. The images with the minimum distance from the base image, according to the chosen distance metric, are retrieved. Regarding the STM images, the extracted features are used to represent the images, and two conventional distance metrics are used: cosine distance and Euclidean distance. Cosine distance is commonly used in information retrieval, where the angle between the two features vectors is used as a measure of divergence between the vectors, and the cosine of this angle is used as the numeric similarity (Singhal, 2001). The cosine similarity between two vectors x and y in an n -dimensional space is given by:

$$S_{cos}(x, y) = \frac{x \cdot y}{\|x\| \|y\|} \quad (4.1)$$

Where the cosine distance is given by:

$$f(x, y) = 1 - S_{cos}(x, y) \quad (4.2)$$

The Euclidean distance in an n-dimensional space between two vectors p and q is given by:

$$d(p, q) = \sqrt{(p_1 - q_1)^2 + (p_2 - q_2)^2 + \dots + (p_n - q_n)^2} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (p_i - q_i)^2} \quad (4.3)$$

The methodology used to validate the extracted features involves random sampling without the repetition of images. At every trial, one image is sampled and a set of similar images is retrieved, ranked in ascending order based on the distance computed between features. Two different tests were performed for each distance metric, using a different combination of trials and numbers of similar images extracted. The choice of these two tests is characterized by the presence of a high number of similar images in the dataset, derived, for example, from sequences of images taken to record a reaction or by changing different microscope parameters to improve image quality. The results could be biased using only 20 images in the retrieval stage; hence a second test with 100 images was chosen. The first test involved 500 trials and a set of 20 similar images, while the second test uses 100 trials and a set of 100 images, so in both cases, the total amount of images retrieved is 10,000. These tests were performed for 16 of the 18 categories identified in the labeling process, where for every category, the samples must belong to the same category while there is no constraint with respect to similar images. Two categories are omitted because their respective total number of images is not enough to perform the first test: *CO_O_Rh110* with 332 images, and *CeO2_mica* with 280 images. The results are quite reassuring, as shown in Figure 4.13 and 4.14, where the results of the two tests are depicted using

the Euclidean distance metric. The red line represents the distribution of the images between categories, while the blue histogram bins are the number of images retrieved for each category, with the green one representing the correct category.

Figure 4.13: First test, 500 trials of a set of 20 similar images using Euclidean distance.

The images extracted from the right label are far more than the normal distribution, which can be interpreted in two ways. First, the representation of the images from the extracted features captures some distinctive information for almost every category. Secondly, many of the categories obtained with the labeling process can be considered of good quality because there is a clear distinction among them. The comparison between the two tests is summarized in Table 4.1, which shows the accuracy for both tests and their difference for each category.

Figure 4.14: Second test, 100 trials of a set of 100 similar images using Euclidean distance.

The best results are achieved by *O_Rh110*, with an accuracy of 69.4% in the first test and 66.44% in the second. There are four other categories where the extracted images are consistently correct in both tests: *NO_NH3_Pt111*, *Gr_Ni111*, *Oxide_Rh110*, and *CeO2111*. This result indicates that images in these categories are well defined, in the sense that their representation as data points in the features space are both close to each other and distant from other data points. *NFFA_ID67* has a remarkable accuracy of 65.99% in the first test, while the second test results are relatively low, with only 39.78%. The delta between the two tests is -26,21%, two times greater than the mean delta of -11.08%. By looking at the subgraphs of the two categories, the drop in the accuracy can be attributed to the confusion with *NO_NH3_Pt111*.

Category	Accuracy (%)		
	500x20	100x100	delta
CO_Gr_Ni111	21.36	13.9	-7.46
CeO2111	41.67	30.52	-11.15
CeO2_Cu111	24.05	13.71	-10.34
CeO2_Pt111	15.52	9.04	-6.48
Gr_Ir100	27	17.16	-9.84
Gr_Ni100	35.1	21.16	-13.94
Gr_Ni111	57.98	46.99	-10.99
K_O_Rh110	26.57	16.62	-9.95
NFFA_Bi2Se3	27.1	14.21	-12.89
NFFA_ID67	65.99	39.78	-26.21
NO_NH3_Pt111	60.47	48.13	-12.34
N_Gr_Ni111	14.49	7.25	-7.24
O_Rh110	69.4	66.44	-2.96
Oxide_Rh110	56.7	46.25	-10.45
Rh_Gr_Ir111	34.28	21.55	-12.73
TBrPP_Au111	27.39	15.00	-12.39

Table 4.1: Euclidean distance metric. Accuracy of first test, second test, and their difference.

The same effect is reflected in *NO_NH3_Pt111*, but to a less extent, probably due to the much higher number of images present in this category. Moreover, it is interesting to note that the best results are achieved for those categories with the higher number of images. Some other categories are challenging, like *CeO2_Pt111*, which is confused with *CeO2111*, probably because the samples composition is quite similar. The same consideration applies to *Gr_Ir100* with respect to *Gr_Ni111*, and for *K_O_Rh110* as compared with *O_Rh110*. All of these categories are small in size compared to the category they are confused with, and they also share one common material. These two conditions indicate that a categories refactoring can be beneficial, where these smaller categories are merged into the larger ones. A more refined division can then be made, creating hierarchical labeling that follows the material compositions more closely. Nonetheless, the results of these tests confirm the reliability of the extracted features, which are used to obtain exact labels for several images in the next section.

4.5 Improved labeling workflow based on image retrieval

The results obtained from the analysis of the features were used to model a new labeling workflow, which exploits the content-based image retrieval described in the previous section. The labeling method involves three distinct steps that are repeated for each category: first, researchers choose a subset of manually labeled images; then, a small group of similar images is retrieved for each one of them; finally, the extracted images are verified by researchers. This system was designed to quickly obtain several manually labeled images while minimizing the amount of work of researchers. The first step is difficult, as finding good images representing a given category is a challenging task; however, the number of images to select is purposely small. The second step is fully automatic and retrieves many images using the similarity method shown in the previous section. The main advantage is in the last step, where researchers have just to verify if the extracted images belong to the picked category, which is much faster than manually selecting the same amount of images from the whole dataset. Finally, the reliability of this workflow was confirmed based on the previous section results, which indicates that a good amount of the images retrieved should be correct. At the time of writing, researchers have manually selected ten representative images for four different categories; for each of these images, the cosine similarity has been used to retrieve the 24 nearest images. It is important to note that a few constraints were added to identify a similar image as valid: it can have the same date as the representative one, but the scan coordinates on the sample must be different, so that a different surface area of the same sample is shown. The metadata used to construct this filter are *XOffset* and *YOffset*. Then, for every representative image, a plot of 5x5 was created with the image at the center and the similar ones around it. Lastly, these graphs were given to the researchers for manual verification. A title identifies every image in the plot with date, file name, and image ID. This layout was chosen as it enables easy comparison between images and thus faster labeling; an example of these plots is shown in Figure 4.15, where the central image represents a sample of graphene (Gr) on nickel (Ni111).

Figure 4.15: Gr_Ni111 category, the center image is representative while others are retrieved by cosine similarity and, in this case, are all correct

The images extracted amount to 960 and, after the manual verification was completed, 560 of these turned out as belonging to the right category. Nonetheless, some of these images were present in more than one graph as they were nearest to several representative images. The total number of correct images without repetition drops from 560 to 454 that is still a remarkable 53%. An overview of the results obtained for each category is shown in Figure 4.16, where for each category, correct images are depicted in green, doubles in yellow, wrongs in red.

Figure 4.16: Cosine similarity results for each category of representative images. Correct, double, and wrong images are in green, yellow, and red respectively.

The high number of doubles in *Gr_Ni100* and *NFFA_ID67* suggests that the representative images are closed to each other in the features space. If this is the case, many images are selected repeatedly in the retrieval stage of these categories as they lie near more than one representative image. Nonetheless, an analysis of the distance between the data points representing the images in the features space is required to better assess the retrieval results. A common approach used to perform this evaluation involves creating two distance heatmaps: one between the discrete representation of the images and another between the images data points in the feature spaces (Aversa, Coronica et al., 2020). The first heatmap representing the discrete distance between categories is generated by comparing each image category against all the others: if they are the same, the distance is 0 otherwise 1. The second heatmap, which represents the distance between the images data points in the feature spaces, is calculated using the cosine distance between the images features, normalized between 0 and 1. The color map encodes the zero distance as black; higher values result in a monotonically increase in the luminance through blue, purple, and yellow hues. In both heatmaps, the images are sorted by category, so in the discrete heatmap, there are present black squares along the diagonal, which represent the zero distance between images of the same category. Similarly, only the diagonal is black in the euclidean distance heatmap, representing the zero distance between an image and itself.

The evaluation metric used to compare the two heatmaps is the Pearson correlation coefficient, calculated as follows:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x - m_x)(y - m_y)}{\sqrt{\sum(x - m_x)^2 \sum(y - m_y)^2}} \quad (4.4)$$

where m_x is the mean of the vector x , and m_y is the mean of the vector y . This coefficient measures the linear relationship between two vectors; the score is between -1 and +1 with 0 implying no correlation. A coefficient of -1 or +1 indicates an exact linear relationship, so in our particular example, a score of 1 means that the two heatmaps are identical. Figure 4.17 and Figure 4.18 show distance heatmaps for the representative and the extracted images, respectively, to better understand the result of the image retrieval method.

Figure 4.17: Distance matrix of 10 representative images from 4 categories, from top to bottom of diagonal: N_Gr_Ni111, Gr_Ni100, Gr_Ni111, NFFA_ID67

Figure 4.18: Distance matrix of 454 extracted images from 4 categories, from top to bottom of diagonal: *N_Gr_Ni111*, *Gr_Ni100*, *Gr_Ni111*, *NFFA_ID67*

Pearson correlation coefficient shows a similar score: 0.423 for the representative images and 0.436 for the extracted images, which consist of a significant relationship with their discrete heatmaps. The heatmap of the cosine distance for representative images shows that several images are distant from all the other images, roughly three for each category, except for *NFFA_ID67* with only one of these images. In general, the second and fourth categories are well defined, as the intra-categorical distance is lower than the inter-categorical. The first category, *N_Gr_Ni111*, shows a correlation with the last one, *NFFA_ID67*, since four of its images are close to several of the other category. This last correlation is not visible in the heatmap of the cosine distance for the extracted images, while there is a correlation between *N_Gr_Ni111* and *Gr_Ni111* that was not present before. Lastly, *Gr_Ni100* and *NFFA_ID67* show low intra-categorical distance as in the previous heatmap. In summary, these results indicate that if the distance between representative images of a category is low, extracted images of the same category should also be closer to each other. Nonetheless, this information seems unrelated with the accuracy of the retrieval method, which is slightly lower for the second category than the third one. Further analysis is required to understand better the role of representative images in the accuracy of the retrieval method. One viable approach is to inspect

the extracted images further, comparing the representative images with the wrong images discarded in the third step of manual validation. In general, the proposed method was still successful, with some categories which performed better than others. However, the significant amount of repeated images is an inefficiency that weighs on researchers, which have to manually verify the same images more than one time. One essential improvement of this process consists in modifying the retrieval step, so that the extraction of an image is not allowed more than once. This workflow is still ongoing for the remaining categories; for two of them, the representative images have already been identified; the similar images plots have been created while the extracted images are currently in the stage of manual label verification.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

This thesis have developed different services and tools that increase the overall value of the dataset of STM images by implementing many aspects of the FAIR data principles into different phases of the data life cycle. In particular, the first activity addressed the general usability and findability of the images by extracting the instrument metadata present for every image of the dataset. These metadata were linked to the underlying images already hosted on the data management infrastructure of CNR-IOM and then stored in a MySQL database directly accessible from any browser. This service was then adjusted to address the needs of the research group in charge of the dataset, which can now easily search and retrieve images from their metadata or insert new metadata fields. The consequent important improvement for the accessibility and usability of the dataset involved the creation of the STM metadata explorer, a publicly available web service to visually explore images metadata through easy to understand graphs. The functionality of the web app, and its significance as an interaction tool with the dataset, are then further improved to include the visualization of images directly on the browser without the need of custom software. Then, after an analysis of the representation of the images and their artifacts, a novel method to detect a particular type of image artifact is developed and presented. Finally, this work addressed the most important missing metadata about the STM images, which is the samples elemental composition. Thanks to strict cooperation with the research group, a labeling scheme of 18 categories of samples were designed, and a labeling workflow was planned and quickly developed to obtain the first 454 manually labeled images of the STM dataset. The achievements of this

work show the importance of good data management practice in scientific research in order to improve the reusability and overall value of the generated data. The data services created for the STM images are currently in use by the researchers, increasing the overall research productivity. Moreover, the web service structure of the STM explorer is already reused to serve another dataset of scientific images, the SEM dataset, available on the TriDAS website. These services are designed around metadata and thus can be implemented with other scientific datasets, regardless of the data type in which the information is stored.

The objectives achieved in this work improve the dataset FAIRification, but there are still essential steps that could be taken. It would be crucial, for example, to implement a user management system (UMS) for the web service and the metadata database, possibly integrated with the one currently in use for the STM dataset. A UMS ensures the accessibility of the data through user authentication and privileges while at the same time improving reusability by maintaining data provenance. Finally, another objective, critical for improving reusability, is the declaration of the data usage license, which expresses the condition under which the STM dataset can be used. Accomplishing these goals would extend the reach of the dataset and its services to the whole scientific community, both for researchers and automated data scraping tools. Following this perspective, the results obtained in the labeling process of the STM images are fundamental, as the category of an image is the most common metadata used to retrieve them. A significant improvement can be achieved with further analysis of the subset of images already labeled. The labeling process resulted in the classification into four different categories of 454 images recorded in 71 days. As previously stated, researchers record images from samples of the same category during a typical working day. Thus, generally, images recorded on the same day are expected to belong to the same category. Therefore, almost all the 8646 images recorded in these 71 days should belong to one of the four categories investigated. Table 5.1 shows an overview of these images, where in the first column are grouped by the tentative category assigned in the coarse labeling, and in the second column are grouped based on the category of the manually labeled images.

Categories	Labeling method	
	Coarse	Manual
Gr_Ni111	3689	4903
NFFA_ID67	1595	1464
Gr_Ni100	1437	1437
Gr_Ir100	909	0
Gr_CO_Gr_Ni111	347	0
N_Gr_Ni111	312	842
NO_NH3_Pt111	209	0
TBrPP_Au111	148	0

Table 5.1: Number of images grouped by category: coarse method and category derived from the manually labeled images

Based on this assumption, a possible approach to validate this hypothesis involves training a classifier, for example, the ResNet-50 model already used in this dataset, on the set of manually labeled images. The model can then be used to classify the set of 8646 images in the four categories. Finally, the classification results are grouped by day and compared to the category of the manually verified image. If a reasonable number of images on a given day are classified with the same category of the manually verified image of that day, then all grouped images can be labeled as belonging to that category. A more straightforward method can involve the labeling of images based only on the number of manually labeled images: if, for a given day, most of the images have been already manually classified into the same category, all images on that day can be labeled accordingly. The importance of metadata is evident in the described solutions, which otherwise would be impossible to implement. Consequently, completing the labeling process started in this work is crucial for further enhancing the dataset. This goal, in particular, is necessary for the reusability of the dataset towards the development of novel tools to identify and recognize specific features within the images. One of such tools could be, for example, an STM image classifier that can be used to classify images automatically once recorded.

References

- Aversa, Rossella, Piero Coronica et al. (2020). ‘Deep Learning, Feature Learning, and Clustering Analysis for SEM Image Classification’. In: *Data Intelligence*, pp. 513–528 (cit. on p. 50).
- Aversa, Rossella, Mohammad Hadi Modarres et al. (2018). ‘Data descriptor: The first annotated set of scanning electron microscopy images for nanoscience’. In: *Sci. Data* 5. ISSN: 20524463. DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2018.172 (cit. on p. 7).
- Bayer, Michael (2012). ‘SQLAlchemy’. In: *The Architecture of Open Source Applications Volume II: Structure, Scale, and a Few More Fearless Hacks*. Ed. by Amy Brown and Greg Wilson. aosabook.org. URL: <http://aosabook.org/en/sqlalchemy.html> (cit. on p. 16).
- Bengio, Yoshua, Aaron Courville and Pascal Vincent (2013). ‘Representation learning: A review and new perspectives’. In: *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* 35.8, pp. 1798–1828. ISSN: 01628828. DOI: 10.1109/TPAMI.2013.50. arXiv: 1206.5538 (cit. on p. 41).
- Benson, Dennis A. et al. (2013). ‘GenBank’. In: *Nucleic Acids Res.* 41.D1, pp. 36–42. ISSN: 03051048. DOI: 10.1093/nar/gks1195 (cit. on p. 2).
- Berman, Helen, Kim Henrick and Haruki Nakamura (2003). ‘Announcing the worldwide Protein Data Bank’. In: *Nat. Struct. Biol.* 10.12, p. 980. ISSN: 10728368. DOI: 10.1038/nsb1203-980 (cit. on p. 2).
- Binnig, G et al. (1982). ‘Tunneling through a controllable vacuum gap’. In: 178, pp. 10–13. DOI: 10.1063/1.92999 (cit. on p. 8).
- Bishop, Christopher (2006). *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*. Springer-Verlag New York, pp. 1–738. ISBN: 978-1-4939-3843-8 (cit. on p. 41).
- Bokeh Development Team (2020). *Bokeh: Python library for interactive visualization*. URL: <https://bokeh.org/> (cit. on p. 24).
- Classifier, SEM (n.d.). *SEM Classifier: Automatic classification of your SEM images*. URL: <https://www.trieste.nffa.eu/the-project/data-services/sem-classifier/> (cit. on p. 21).
- CNR-IOM (n.d.). *Istituto Officina dei Materiali (IOM) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR)*. URL: <https://www.iom.cnr.it/> (cit. on pp. 6, 7, 11).

- Delisle, Marc (2012). *Mastering phpMyAdmin 3.4 for effective MySQL management*. Packt Publishing Ltd (cit. on pp. 15, 19).
- Deng, J et al. (2009). ‘ImageNet: A large-scale hierarchical image database’. In: *2009 IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit.* Pp. 248–255. DOI: 10.1109/CVPR.2009.5206848 (cit. on p. 42).
- European Commission (2016). ‘H2020 Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020’. In: (cit. on p. 2).
- (2018). *Turning FAIR into reality*. ISBN: 9789279965470. DOI: 10.2777/1524 (cit. on p. 2).
- EUSMI (n.d.). *EUSMI: The European Soft Matter Infrastructure*. URL: <https://eusmi-h2020.eu/> (cit. on p. 6).
- Ge, Mengshu et al. (2020). ‘Deep Learning Analysis on Microscopic Imaging in Materials Science’. In: *Materials Today Nano*, p. 100087 (cit. on p. 42).
- Goodfellow, Ian et al. (2016). *Deep learning*. Vol. 1. MIT press Cambridge (cit. on p. 41).
- Grinberg, Miguel (2018). *Flask web development: developing web applications with python*. " O’Reilly Media, Inc." (cit. on p. 21).
- He, Kaiming et al. (2016). ‘Deep residual learning for image recognition’. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pp. 770–778 (cit. on p. 42).
- Howard, Jeremy and Sylvain Gugger (2020). ‘Fastai: A layered API for deep learning’. In: *Information* 11.2, p. 108 (cit. on p. 42).
- Jacobsen, Annika et al. (Nov. 2019). ‘A Generic Workflow for the Data FAIRification Process’. In: *Data Intell.* 2.1-2, pp. 56–65. DOI: 10.1162/dint_a_00028. URL: https://doi.org/10.1162/dint%7B%5C_%7Da%7B%5C_%7D00028 (cit. on p. 4).
- Kluyver, Thomas et al. (2016). ‘Jupyter Notebooks—a publishing format for reproducible computational workflows.’ In: *ELPUB*, pp. 87–90 (cit. on p. 19).
- Krogh, Jesper Wisborg, Krogh and Gennick (2018). *MySQL Connector/Python Revealed*. Springer (cit. on p. 15).
- Laney, Doug (2005). ‘3D data management: Controlling data volume, velocity and variety’. In: February 2001 (cit. on p. 2).
- LeCun, Yann et al. (1989). ‘Generalization and network design strategies’. In: *Connect. Perspect.* Pp. 143–155. ISBN: 978-0444880611 (cit. on p. 41).
- LeCun, Yann, Yoshua Bengio and Geoffrey Hinton (2015). ‘Deep learning’. In: *Nature* 521.7553, pp. 436–444. ISSN: 1476-4687. DOI: 10.1038/nature14539. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539> (cit. on p. 41).

- Liu, Ling and M Tamer Özsu (2009). *Encyclopedia of database systems*. Vol. 6. Springer New York, NY, USA: (cit. on p. 3).
- Magazine, D-Lib (2011). ‘The dataverse network®: an open-source application for sharing, discovering and preserving data’. In: *D-lib Magazine* 17.1/2 (cit. on p. 2).
- McKinney, Wes (2010). ‘Data Structures for Statistical Computing in Python’. In: *Proceedings of the 9th Python in Science Conference*. Ed. by Stéfan van der Walt and Jarrod Millman, pp. 56–61. DOI: 10.25080/Majora-92bf1922-00a (cit. on p. 16).
- Mirco Panighel (2020a). *Omicronscala: A python package to read and parse .par files from Omicron*. URL: <https://gitlab.com/mpanighel/omicronscala/> (cit. on p. 14).
- (2020b). *Spym: A python package for processing Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM) data*. URL: <https://github.com/mpanighel/spym> (cit. on p. 31).
- Modarres, Mohammad Hadi et al. (2017). ‘Neural Network for Nanoscience Scanning Electron Microscope Image Recognition’. In: *Sci. Rep.* September, pp. 1–12. ISSN: 2045-2322. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-017-13565-z. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-13565-z> (cit. on pp. 7, 42).
- Nanoscience Instruments (n.d.). *Scanning Tunneling Microscopy*. URL: <https://www.nanoscience.com/techniques/scanning-tunneling-microscopy/> (cit. on p. 8).
- NextCloud (n.d.). *NextCloud: on-premises file share and collaboration platform*. URL: <https://nextcloud.com/> (cit. on p. 6).
- NFFA-EUROPE (n.d.). *NFFA: Nanoscience Foundries and Fine Analysis*. URL: <https://www.nffa.eu/> (cit. on pp. 6, 7).
- Pan, S J and Q Yang (2010). ‘A Survey on Transfer Learning’. In: *IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng.* 22.10, pp. 1345–1359. ISSN: 1558-2191 VO - 22. DOI: 10.1109/TKDE.2009.191 (cit. on p. 41).
- Paszke, Adam et al. (2019). ‘Pytorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library’. In: *Advances in neural information processing systems*, pp. 8026–8037 (cit. on p. 42).
- Rodani, Tommaso (Sept. 2020). *t0m-R/STM_images 0.1.0*. Version 0.1.0. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4019641. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4019641> (cit. on pp. ii, 12).
- ScientaOmicron (n.d.). *LT STM Lab*. URL: <https://scientaomicron.com/en/system-solutions/SPM/LT-STM-Lab> (cit. on p. 10).
- Sefraoui, Omar, Mohammed Aissaoui and Mohsine Eleuldj (2012). ‘OpenStack: toward an open-source solution for cloud computing’. In: *International Journal of Computer Applications* 55.3, pp. 38–42 (cit. on p. 15).

- Singhal, Amit (2001). ‘Modern Information Retrieval: A Brief Overview’. In: *Bull. IEEE Comput. Soc. Tech. Comm. Data Eng.* 24.4, pp. 35–43 (cit. on p. 43).
- TriDAS (n.d.). *Trieste Advance Data Services*. URL: <https://tridas.nffa.eu/> (cit. on p. 20).
- Van Rossum, Guido and Fred L. Drake (2009). *Python 3 Reference Manual*. Scotts Valley, CA: CreateSpace. ISBN: 1441412697 (cit. on p. 12).
- Wan, Ji et al. (2014). ‘Deep learning for content-based image retrieval : A comprehensive study’. In: (cit. on p. 43).
- Wenger, Marc et al. (1999). ‘ASTRONOMY AND The SIMBAD astronomical database The CDS Reference Database for Astronomical Objects’. In: 23, pp. 1–14. arXiv: 0002110v1 [arXiv:astro-ph] (cit. on p. 2).
- Werner, A et al. (2003). ‘Theories of scanning probe microscopes at the atomic scale’. In: DOI: 10.1103/revmodphys.75.1287 (cit. on p. 9).
- Widenius, Michael, Davis Axmark and Paul DuBois (2002). *Mysql Reference Manual*. 1st. USA: O’Reilly & Associates, Inc. ISBN: 0596002653 (cit. on p. 15).
- Wilkinson, Mark D (2016). ‘Comment : The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship’. In: pp. 1–9. DOI: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (cit. on pp. 2, 3).
- Zenodo (n.d.). *Zenodo*. URL: <https://zenodo.org/> (cit. on p. 2).